

SCADA BASED GENERATOR STATOR WATER COOLING PUMP CONTROL SYSTEM

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Abstract:

The power station Generator will be a high capacity machine. Because of the enormous current handling capacity, in terms of thousands of amperes- heat generation will be more. Hence cooling of generator plays vital role. Failure in cooling arrangement will result in tripping of the generator from grid. Monitoring Stator water cooling system is efficient with customized SCADA package and Introducing Programmable Logic Controller as a control platform.

Key Words: Generator, Control, Pump & Programmable Logic Controller

1. Introduction:

One method of taking away the losses from the windings of any electrical machines is by direct cooling using water. The optimum design of large capacity turbo-generator, as a rule envisages water cooling of stator windings. The generators employ a closed loop circulation of High quality De-Mineralized water through the stator windings made of hollow and solid conductors. The cooling system circuit uses either Distilled water or Fully De-Mineralized water from WTP, which is free from Oxygen. The pressure and flow of DM water from and to the generator will be monitored through pressure switches and flow meter. The conductivity of DM water should also being monitored and it should not exceed 2.5 micro mho/cm. Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of existing stator water cooling system. The stator water cooling system comprises of following main components:

- ✓ Two 3 phase drive of 9.3 KW for DM water pumping application of 100% duty cycle. One in service and other kept as reserve.
- ✓ Two vacuum pump drives for creating vacuum in Expansion tank. One will be in service – another kept as reserve back-up. Two DM water cooler (Exchangers) of 100% duty cycle.
- ✓ Polishing Unit.
- ✓ Mechanical Filters.
- ✓ Magnetic Filter.
- ✓ Raw water for Exchangers.

Other components employed in the system are Gas trap device, Expansion tank, water jet ejector, valves and associated instrumentation. Together with the pipe work these components form the external circuit for the supply of cooling water to generator windings.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of stator water cooling system

It is proposed to monitor Stator water cooling system with customized SCADA package (Hardware & Software) and Programmable Logic Controller is introduced as a control platform. We plan to do our project in the above area with SCADA based implementation. For controlling we introduce Programmable logic controllers. PLCs, have become the industry standard, replacing the hard-wired electromechanical devices, in controlling complicated process machines. PLCs are playing ever-popular and critical roles in modern

manufacturing systems. Introducing PLC our process becomes PC friendly (Human Machine Interface-HMI) and the control becomes user-friendly SCADA is a computer system that supervises and controls industrial system. It usually supervises data from various sensors. The brain of the supervisory control and data acquisition control systems are operated by the Remote Terminal Units – often referred as RTUs. The RTUs consists of a programmable Logic Controllers.

2. Objective:

- ✓ To design a pump controller operating system using Programmable Logic Controller and SCADA.
- ✓ The existing system pumps are controlled by relays to be replaced with SCADA system which will monitor and control the Pumps.

3. Existing Scheme:

Figure 2: Stator Water Cooling System with Relay control

Most of the existing stator cooling pumps are controlled by either by manual operation or by Relays. A relay is an electrically operated switch. Relays with multiple operating coils are used to protect electrical circuits from overload or faults. Fig.2. shows the actual circuit diagram for SWP-A/B control using relays and timers. In that 4C is the power contactor and 21R, 22R, 23R, 24R are the control relays.

Limitations of Relay Logic:

- ✓ Most of the Relay control system requires large space.
- ✓ Very little or no flexibility for carrying out field alteration of system logic.
- ✓ Frequent maintenance requirement.

Need For PLC:

- ✓ In all type of Industries, Electrical process and Instrumentation process are the predominant processes. Systems by which these processes are monitored effectively are called control Technologies.
- ✓ PLC's are highly reliable, fast and flexible.
- ✓ PLC can handle severe conditions.
- ✓ PLC can converse with other controllers.
- ✓ PLC's are easy to program and troubleshoot.
- ✓ They include display units.

4. Proposed Scheme:

A. Block Diagram:

Figure 3: Stator Water Cooling System with scada

The proposed stator water cooling system with SCADA is shown in fig.3. The heat losses occur in the Generator parts are removed by the De-Mineralised (DM) water. DM water from boiler feed water plant. Part of DM water is bypassed, and is treated in mixed bed ion exchanger, connected in Parallel to the stator winding and return into suction side of the water Pump- thus maintaining the conductivity of closed loop circulating water within allowable level. The DM water pump is connected to a three phase ac induction motor. Failure of working pump due to fault or power supply failure results in an automatic starting or changeover to standby pump drive. The condition for such a changeover is the diminishing of DM water pressure at the downstream. It is measured or sensed continuously through a Pressure switch. The heat absorbed by the DM water in the generator is dissipated to the secondary coolant in the primary water cooler. The difference of pressure between two end points such as at inlet and outlet of stator winding is of the amount of choking.

The De-Mineralized water from the outlet of stator winding collected in an Overhead Expansion tank, which provides a constant level of water during normal running of the system. The Hot De-Mineralized water from generator (after cooling) enters the tank through perforated pipe in the form of spray- thus discharges heat and any entrapped gas. A water jet ejector is connected to the expansion tank for creating vacuum for the purpose of removing any traces of Oxygen/Hydrogen, which may be present as a result hydrogen leakage into the DM water stream. DM water flowing through the windings is measured by a orifice plate, flow transducer, flow indicator and recorder. Signaling contacts are existing in flow switch, that are set to annunciate when flow through the windings low. It initiates tripping of the machine at emergency flow on the principles of two out of three Conductivity cell and suitable indicator and recorder, to continuous monitoring of the conductivity of water, which annunciate alarm at conductivity high set value at very high conductivity is tripped automatically. In addition to above, the system also provides for necessary instrumentation for indicating/ signalling of the temperatures and pressures at various points of the system Pressure interlocking of the pumps is also provided.

B. Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC):

Programmable logic controllers are solid-state members of the computer family, using integrated circuits instead of electromechanical components to implement control functions. Since PLC offering the relay functions it replaces the hardwired relays. PLC's met the necessity of modularity, expandability, programmability, and the simplicity of use in an industrial atmosphere. These controllers can be easily installed, which will be used less space. PLCs are used in many "real world" applications. PLC is the best suitable control technology for electrical process in Real-Time applications. A PLC works by continually scanning a program.

5. Conclusion:

While implementing PLC it is quite convenient to control the elements – i.e., circuit breakers, motors. Due to the superior communication facility with PC, system monitoring via computer is possible. Control of elements via PC makes this technology to widespread use in electrical engineering and instrumentation applications. PLC makes the system control with high reliability, relatively at faster speed of data transfer compared to other available technologies and consumes very less power, for its operation. SCADA- Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition System will be the attachable component of PLC, makes the system more visualized and comfortable for general users.

6. References:

1. Gong Xunjie, "The corrosion and protection of the thermal equipment," The Chinese Electrical Power Press, Beijing, 1998.
2. M. S. Thomas, P. Kumar, and V. K. Chandna, "Design, development, and commissioning of a SCADA laboratory for research and training," IEEE Trans. Power Syst., vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 1582–1588, Aug. 2004.
3. Qiu Yingning, Sun Juan, Cao Mengnan, Wang Hao, Feng Yanhui, Yang Wenxian, Infield David "Model Based Wind Turbine Gearbox Fault Detection on SCADA Data"
4. D. C. Osburn, "System and method for communication for a supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system," U.S. Patent 6950851B2, Sep. 27, 2005.